

A FINITE ELEMENT APPROACH TO POSTBUCKLING ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Based on the von Kármán large deformation assumptions, a 72 degree-of-freedom high precision higher order triangular plate element using a simplified higher order shear deformation plate theory is developed for the analysis of postbuckling behavior of composite laminated plate subjected to edge shortening or in-plane compressive loading. By examining the local minimum of total potential energy of each mode, a clear picture of buckled pattern change is presented. Results show that the buckled pattern change may occur for plates with certain material properties and boundary conditions. It also shows that the buckling mode will shift from first to second mode shortly after buckling occurs if the transverse shear deformation is included.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that plate is capable of carrying a much increased load after buckling without failure. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the behavior of the plate after buckling to fully utilize the strength of the plate. A precise analysis of postbuckling behavior is quite difficult due to the use of the nonlinear plate theory and to the buckled pattern changes that occur in the buckled state. In most postbuckling analyses, the buckled pattern of the plate is assumed to remain unchanged. This is only a reasonable assumption in the immediate vicinity of the buckling load. To obtain a detailed analysis of plate response over a wide postbuckling load range, changes in buckling pattern must be taken into consideration. An early discussion of buckled pattern change was presented by Stein¹ for a three-bar-column model subjected to axial compressive load. In his subsequent paper², he concluded that the intersection of the load-shortening curves indicates possible changes in buckled pattern. The postbuckling behavior of composite plates has been discussed by various investigators.³⁻⁷ Among these studies, postbuckling behavior with no buckled pattern change assumption, usually concerns about the relation of in-plane compressive force vs. transverse deflection or in-plane compressive force vs. buckled bending stress. Chia⁸ in 1988, made a review of geometrically nonlinear behavior of composite plates and pointed out that the buckled pattern change may occur if p/p_{cr} is greater than 3.0. Recently, Shin⁹ compared the magnitude of the total potential energy of each buckling mode. The mode which has the minimum value of the total potential energy is assumed

to represent the actual buckled pattern. However, he only checked the first variation of the total potential energy which may not necessarily give the local minimum of the total potential energy. Based on von Kármán large deformation assumptions, a 72 degree-of-freedom high precision triangular plate element developed in Ref. 10 is extended to study the postbuckling behavior of composite laminated plate subjected to edge shortening or in-plane compressive load. The buckled pattern change and the transverse effect are presented.

FORMULATIONS

Based on the simplified higher order plate theory in Ref. 10 and the von Kármán large deflection assumptions, the strain-displacement relations of a laminated plate can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \epsilon_1 \equiv \epsilon_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x} - z \frac{\partial^2 w^b}{\partial x^2} - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \frac{\partial^2 w^s}{\partial x^2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \\
 \epsilon_2 \equiv \epsilon_{yy} &= \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial y} - z \frac{\partial^2 w^b}{\partial y^2} - \frac{4z^3}{3h^2} \frac{\partial^2 w^s}{\partial y^2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \\
 \epsilon_3 \equiv \epsilon_{zz} &= 0 \\
 \epsilon_6 \equiv 2\epsilon_{xy} &= \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x} - 2z \frac{\partial^2 w^b}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{8z^3}{3h^2} \frac{\partial^2 w^s}{\partial x \partial y} + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) \\
 \epsilon_4 \equiv 2\epsilon_{yz} &= \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) \frac{\partial w^s}{\partial y} \\
 \epsilon_5 \equiv 2\epsilon_{xz} &= \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^2} \right) \frac{\partial w^s}{\partial x}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The total strain energy of the laminated plate is

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_v \{\sigma\}^T \{\epsilon\} dv \tag{2}$$

For a composite laminated plate with n layers, the stress-strain relation of k^{th} layer of the plate can be expressed in the plate coordinate system.

$$\{\sigma\}_k = [\bar{Q}]_k \{\epsilon\}_k \tag{3}$$

where \bar{Q}_{ij} are the transformed reduced stiffnesses. By substituting equations (1) and (3) into (2), the total strain energy of a composite laminated plate can be expressed as the sum of quadratic, cubic and quartic displacement functions as

$$U = U_2 + U_3 + U_4 \tag{4}$$

in which U_2 , U_3 , and U_4 can be found in Ref. 10. The work, due to the in-plane loading $p(x, y)$, integrating over the side of the element along which the load is applied, is given as

$$W_c = \int u(x, y) p(x, y) ds \tag{5}$$

and the total potential energy of the laminate is then expressed as

$$\pi = U - W \quad (6)$$

The nonlinear equilibrium equation of the laminated plate can be derived by taking first variation of the total potential energy π of the plate as

$$\delta\pi = 0 \quad (7)$$

and the Hessian matrix of the laminated plate is obtained by taking second variation of the total potential energy of the plates as

$$H = \delta^2\pi \quad (8)$$

If the eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix are all positive, then the system is in stable equilibrium state with its total potential energy in a local minimum stage.

For the present finite element formulation, a 72 d.o.f. triangular element with thickness h as shown in Fig. 1 is used. The lateral displacement within this element is assumed to be the sum of the displacement due to bending and that due to shear deformation. The displacement functions for u , v , w^b and w^s can be expressed in the local $\xi - \eta$ coordinate system as a polynomial to the complete fifth order of ξ and η exclude the term $\xi^4\eta$.

$$u_0 = \sum_{i=1}^{20} \alpha_i \xi^{m_i} \eta^{n_i} \quad v_0 = \sum_{i=1}^{20} \beta_i \xi^{m_i} \eta^{n_i} \quad (9a)$$

$$w^b = \sum_{i=1}^{20} \gamma_i \xi^{m_i} \eta^{n_i} \quad w^s = \sum_{i=1}^{20} \zeta_i \xi^{m_i} \eta^{n_i} \quad (9b)$$

where

$$m_i = (0, 1, 0, 2, 1, 0, 3, 2, 1, 0, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0, 5, 3, 2, 1, 0)$$

$$n_i = (0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 2, 0, 1, 2, 3, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 0, 2, 3, 4, 5)$$

By following the procedure described in Ref. 11, the displacement functions with reference to the global coordinate can be expressed in terms of the element nodal displacement vector $\{q\}$. Substituting the displacement functions in Eqs. (9) into (4) and integrating over the plate element, the total strain energy of an element can be expressed as

$$U_e = \frac{1}{2} \{q\}^T [R] [T] [T]^T \left[[k_l] + \frac{1}{3} [n_1] + \frac{1}{6} [n_2] \right] [T] [R] \{q\} \quad (10)$$

with

$$\{q\}^T = [\{q_u\}^T, \{q_v\}^T, \{q_{w^b}\}^T, \{q_{w^s}\}^T]$$

in which the matrices $[R]$ and $[T]$ are given in Ref. 11, matrices $[k_l]$, $[n_1]$ and $[n_2]$ are the linear, first-order and second-order nonlinear stiffness matrices, respectively. By substituting Eq. (9a) into (5), and integrating along the loading edges of the plate element, the consistent load vector p_f is obtained as

$$\{p_f\} = [R_2]^T [T_2]^T \{p_w\} \quad (11)$$

where the matrices $[R_2]$, $[T_2]$ are submatrices of $[R]$ and $[T]$ and the column vector $\{p_w\}$ is expressed as

$$p_{w_i} = \int \int p \xi^{m_i} \eta^{n_i} d\xi d\eta$$

On assembling the whole element stiffness matrices and load vectors and applying kinematic boundary conditions, the statically nonlinear equilibrium equations may be written as

$$\left[[K_i] + \frac{1}{2}[N_1] + \frac{1}{3}[N_2] \right] \{Q\} = \{P\} \quad (12)$$

In the present study, the Newton-Raphson method is applied to solve this nonlinear system equations.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the following analysis, the plate is modeled by using a 4×4 mesh with 32 elements. The material property for the laminates is $E_1/E_2 = 26.5$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 1.184E_2$, and, $\nu_{12} = 0.21$.

The results shown in Figs. 2 and 3 are the postbuckling behavior curves of a square isotropic plate with edge displacements vs. in-plane forces and eigenvalues. Note that N_x is the in-plane force induced by the edge shortening in the x -direction. λ is the minimum eigenvalue of Hessian matrix and λ_0 is the minimum eigenvalue of Hessian matrix for plate without edge shortening. The loaded edges of the plate are kept straight. The other two edges are stress free for plate in Fig. 2 and kept straight for plate in Fig. 3. The results from Ref. 3 are also shown in the figures as open rectangles for comparison purpose. The lines AB , BC , BD , CE represent the load-shortening curves and their corresponding curves ab , bc , bd , ce are the lowest eigenvalue of the system in its equilibrium state. As the load is increased from zero, the plate remains flat until the load reaches point B . At this bifurcation point, the plate will buckle into first buckling mode due to the equilibrium state of the flat plate becoming unstable. This is also evident from the lines bc and bd that the lowest eigenvalue of the system for the unbuckled plate is negative and for the first buckling mode is positive. After buckling, the plate in Fig. 3 is stiffer than the plate in Fig. 2 due to the in-plane edge constraint of the plate in Fig. 3. Therefore, the slope of line BD in Fig. 3 is higher than that in Fig. 2. If the load is further increased beyond point F in Fig. 3 the plate will remain in the first buckling mode even the load required to maintain the plate in the first mode is higher than that in the second mode. This is due to the fact that the system is in stable condition at this moment and the buckled pattern it will be is depending on the previous deformed buckling shape. However, if there is enough external disturbed force, the buckling mode of the plate may shift from the first mode to the second, i.e., the total potential energy may jump from one local minimum point to another. Fig. 4 shows the postbuckling behaviors of $[0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates. It is seen that both laminates possess the same characteristics as that just stated above for the isotropic plate. From the trends of the eigenvalue curves (not shown in the figure), the second buckling mode of the $[0/90]_s$ laminate is always unstable.

Usually, a square plate will buckle into and remain in the first buckling mode without buckled pattern change if the load is gradually increased and there is no external disturbed forces. However, some plates with certain material properties and boundary conditions, the first buckling mode may become unstable and buckled pattern change may occur. Figs. 5 to 7 show the postbuckling behaviors of square plates subjected to uniaxial in-plane uniform load. The four edges are now not necessary to keep straight. The plates with simply supported boundary conditions show the same postbuckling characteristics as those discussed in the previous section for the edge shortening plates. But the isotropic and $[\pm 45]_s$ laminated plates with clamped edges display a different postbuckling behavior.

When the in-plane load reaches the buckling load, the plates buckle into first the buckling mode. As the load is further increased to a certain value, the plate becomes unstable and buckled pattern change occurs. The buckling mode of the plate is now shifted from the first mode to the second. The plate will remain in the second mode until the loading change makes the plate becoming unstable again.

It is known that transverse shear effect on the mechanic behavior of thick plate is significant. Figs. 8 and 9 show the effect of transverse shear on the buckled pattern change of the above mentioned isotropic and $[\pm 45]_s$ laminated plates with clamped edges. The results obtained using thin plate theory are also presented to indicate the extent of the transverse shear effect. It is seen that the buckled pattern change will occur earlier if the transverse shear deformation is included. The thicker the plate is the earlier the buckled pattern change happens. For $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate with $L/h = 10$, the buckled pattern is changed from the first mode to the second shortly after the buckling occurs. This may be attributed to the fact that the transverse shear deformation will reduce the lateral stiffness of the plate which in turn shifts the point of bifurcation to the left in the deflection-loading curve.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on von Kármán deformation assumptions, a 72 degree-of-freedom (d.o.f.) high precision triangular plate element using a simplified higher order shear deformation plate theory is developed for the analysis of postbuckling behavior of isotropic and composite laminated plates subjected to edge shortening or in-plane compressive load. By examining the local minimum of total potential energy of each mode, a clear picture of buckled pattern change may be seen. From the present results, the following conclusions can be made :

1. By checking the eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix of plate, the instability behavior of plates after buckling can be determined clearly.
2. The combination of loading type (edge shortening or uniform loading) , material properties, and boundary conditions influences the trends and occurrence of the buckled pattern change.
3. The buckled pattern change will occur earlier if the transverse shear deformation is considered. The thicker the plate is, the earlier the buckled pattern change happens.

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Fig. 1 Coordinate system of triangular plate element.

Fig. 2 Postbuckling behavior of square isotropic plate with unloaded edges stress free (---- for $N_x L^2/D$, Δ for λ/λ_0)

Fig. 3 Postbuckling behavior of square isotropic plate with unloaded edges kept straight (---- for $N_x L^2/D$, Δ for λ/λ_0)

Fig. 4 Postbuckling behavior of square laminate with unloaded edges stress free.

Fig. 5 Postbuckling behavior of square isotropic plate.

Fig. 6 Postbuckling behavior of square angle-ply $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 7 Postbuckling behavior of square cross-ply $[0/90]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 8 Postbuckling behavior of square isotropic plate with clamped boundary condition.

Fig. 9 Postbuckling behavior of square laminate $[\pm 45]_s$ with clamped boundary condition.